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Abstract: Tourism has been an essential part of world economy. It offers several benefits, such as, economic contribution, social exchanging and broadening people’s cultural horizons. «Tourism is also an expression of a relevant potential in terms of communication and cultural integration, two important elements in the world that is ever more global» (Angeloni, 2013). Cultural integration means working and sharing ideas with different cultural backgrounds. In fact, this research investigates the overall positive and negative effects of tourism development with how to prevent cultures from latter ones in the modern era.

Key words: Tourism, industry, culture, UNESCO, infrastructure.

Annotatsiya: Turizm jahon iqtisodiyotining ajralmas qismiga aylanib ulgurgan. Bu soha bir necha foydali jihatlar, jumladan, iqtisodiyotga hissa, ijtimoiy va madaniy almashinuv, insoniyatning dunyoqarashini kengaytirishga hissa qo‘shadi. «Turizm, shuningdek, aloqa va madaniy integratsiya nuqtai nazaridan tegishli potentsialning ifodasidir, dunyoning ikki muhim elementi bo‘lib, ular tobora global bo‘lib bormoqda» (Angeloni, 2013). Madaniy integratsiya turli xil madaniy kelib chiqishi bilan ishlash va fikr almashishni anglatadi. Aslida, bu tadqiqot turizm rivojlanishining umumiy ijobiy va salbiy ta'sirini zamonaviy davrda madaniyatlarning oldini olish bilan o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Turizm, sanoat, madaniyat, YUNESKO, infratuzilma.

Аннотация: Туризм всегда был важной частью мировой экономики. Он предоставляет различные преимущества, такие как, экономический вклад, обмен социума и расширение культурного кругозора людей. "Туризм также является выражением значительного потенциала с точки зрения коммуникации и культурной интеграции, двух важных элементов в мире, который становится всё более глобальным" (Angeloni, 2013). Культурная интеграция означает совместную работу и обмен идеями между людьми с разным культурным происхождением. Настоящее исследование рассматривает общие положительные и отрицательные эффекты

развития туризма, а также способы предотвращения негативных последствий для культур в современную эпоху.

Ключевые слова: туризм, индустрия, культура, ЮНЕСКО, инфраструктура.

The benefits of tourism industry

Tourism have created the best opportunities to both developed and developing nations. Recent statistics show that countries which possess rich cultural heritage and attractive tourism destinations have significantly benefited from tourism sector. An explanation of the world's tourism destinations reveals that in 2010 International arrivals (43,626 million) were determined and spent (38,786 trillion dollars) by tourists in Italy (UNWTO, 2011). As an example of one of the developing countries, India has also succeeded to make a profit from tourist flow. Below table illustrates how India were able to improve its financial stagnation. Although tourism was not the primary resource for India, it got higher profit than Kenya and Nigeria.

Tourism is also a key component to develop people's cross cultural and intercultural communication skills. According to Kamol Mustayev, "the study of different styles is cross-cultural, and the cultures interacting with one another is intercultural" In recent times, most visitors want to learn about other cultural areas, such as, traditions, social situations and etc. Their needs are based on the involvement of host community. Most nations find this kind of situations as a problem, but it is the way of giving chance to their citizens. If tourists and usual people communicate each other, this situation would lead to the mutual development. Building complex communication might not be in the first place, creating friendly atmosphere and understanding the needs between tourist and local people should be prioritized. Using this kind of new approaches in tourism sector called "creative tourism". The study by UNESCO reveals tourists' interest towards attractive places is decreasing, but rising towards getting deep experiences.

Some nations have experienced difficulties in the way of tourism development. The primary reason is more and more countries have invested for increasing the attractiveness of their tourism destinations. Their main goal from this investment is to make a new "economic driver" for their financial growth. The research from the study of Kenya's tourism industry shows that communities in Kenya have benefited directly from tourism while other ones in Nigeria has not made a profit. The motive is that at time, social instability did not exist in Kenya whereas, Nigeria has political instability, violence, ethnic

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rivalry, and crime. These two examples clarify that the social situation also plays an important role in the tourism industry.

The negative turns of tourism

Tourism has been contributing to the spreading of some issues. The most common

ones are traffic congestion, pollution, increasing the cost of living and others which are related to culture and society. Thinking about approaches to solve these problems is based on making strategic plans. In recent times, most nations have failed to make huge income on tourism sector. Because they prefer taking money rather than to make great opportunities for tourists. This can be an underlying factor to why some think tourism not invaluable for economics. In this case, one thing is clear that countries which have above mentioned issues are paying attention to just for financial improvement than making better infrastructure design. “The cultural development of a territory in many cases becomes central to tourists’ decisions on whether to visit it, but also for residents to decide whether to live there. In fact, culture is the major factor in the attractiveness of most destinations, not only in terms of tourism, but also in attracting residents and inward investment” (OECD, 2009). This point clarifies tourist flow is not completely responsible for these destination-related issues, policymakers and host community are also equally responsible.

Conclusion

Tourism has both merits and demerits. One of the primary benefits is all nations can reach to financial advancement. Then, they can preserve their cultural heritage while they represent them more to the public. Tourism industry also create problems with pollution, traffic congestion, increasing the cost of living and others. The solutions to these matters are to be made certain rules by Governments, and providing whether society and tourists are following them. Because residents can be also guilty. Therefore, making strict laws on these issues and the provision of whether everyone is respecting them are the solutions.

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